

Francesca Saggini (University of Edinburgh).

Romantic Resources: Theatre and Drama. A record for scholars and students. (In progress.)

The following list records free or Open Access resources available on the internet. Other than when stated, all links were active on 14 June 2022. Further resources will be added to the list as my research progresses.

Burckert, Mattie (Director). *The London Stage Database* <https://londonstagedatabase.uoregon.edu/>. Open access and open-source database that makes it possible to search the seminal, 11-volume *The London Stage, 1660-1800: A Calendar of Plays, Entertainments & Afterpieces, Together with Casts, Box-Receipts and Contemporary Comment. Compiled from the Playbills, Newspapers and Theatrical Diaries of the Period* (Southern Illinois University Press, 1960-1968).

Burckert, Mattie. "Recovering the London Stage Information Bank: Lessons from an Early Humanities Computing Project." *DHQ: Digital Humanities Quarterly* 11, 3 (2017).
<http://www.digitalhumanities.org/dhq/vol/11/3/000321/000321.html>

Burwick, Frederick. *Romantic Drama: Acting and Reacting*. Available to read online <https://silo.pub/romantic-drama-acting-and-reacting.html> (Please, make sure you abide by any copyright restrictions before downloading.)

Cook, Daniel | Dellarosa, Franca | Van Kooy, Dana. *Teaching Romanticism XXVIII: Drama, part 4*.
<http://www.romtext.org.uk/teaching-romanticism-xxviii-drama-part> *Romantic Textualities: Literature and Print Culture, 1780–1840*

Cook, Daniel | Parker, Deven M. | Van Kooy, Dana. *Teaching Romanticism XXVII: Drama, part 3*.
<http://www.romtext.org.uk/teaching-romanticism-xxvii-drama-part-> *Romantic Textualities: Literature and Print Culture, 1780–1840*

Cook, Daniel | Piccitto, Diane | Van Kooy, Dana. *Teaching Romanticism XXVI: Drama, part 2*.
<http://www.romtext.org.uk/teaching-romanticism-xxvi-drama-part-2/> *Romantic Textualities: Literature and Print Culture, 1780–1840*

Cook, Daniel | Van Kooy, Dana. *Teaching Romanticism XXV: Drama, part 1*.
<http://www.romtext.org.uk/teaching-romanticism-xxv-drama-part-1/> *Romantic Textualities: Literature and Print Culture, 1780–1840*

Craddock, Patricia and students: *The World of London Theatre, 1660-1800*. Voice of the Shuttle.
<http://vos.ucsb.edu/browse.asp?id=2569>. The site was down at the time of compiling this record.

Crochunis Thomas & Michael Eberle-Sinatra. "Putting Plays (And More) In Cyberspace: An Overview of the British Women Playwrights around 1800 Project," *European Romantic Review*, 14:1 (2003), 117-131, DOI: 10.1080/10509580303680. Download provided by
<https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/151554489.pdf>

Crochunis, Thomas C. (ed.) *British Women Playwrights around 1800: New Paradigms and Recoveries*. A special issue of *Romanticism on the Net*. Issue 12 (1998) <https://ronjournal.org/articles/n12/> . A series of essays looking at the "paradigm shifts" in the areas of women's playwriting and theatre authorship.

Crochunis, Thomas C. (ed.) *Teaching Romantic Drama*. Special issue of *Romantic Pedagogies Commons* (May 2011). <https://romantic-circles.org/pedagogies/commons/theatre>

Drama Online <https://www.dramaonlinelibrary.com/national-theatre-learning-resources> . An award-winning, multimedia digital library of drama resources.

Falk, Michael. 'Sad Realities: The Romantic Tragedies of Charles Harpur', *Romantic Textualities: Literature and Print Culture, 1780–1840*, 23 (Summer 2020). [PDF DOI:10.18573/romtext.65](https://doi.org/10.18573/romtext.65) (9 August 2020). http://www.romtext.org.uk/articles/rt23_n12/ . Discusses two tragedies by Australian author Charles Harpur: *The Bushrangers* (1853, orig. 1835), a gothic bandit drama, and the incomplete *King Saul* (c. 1838), apparently inspired by Byron's *Cain*.

Halliwell, John and Ian Haywood (eds) *Romantic Spectacle*. A special issue of *Romanticism on the Net*. Issue 46 (2007) <https://ronjournal.org/articles/n46/>

Hewitt, Regina (ed.) *Joanna Baillie and Utopianism*. Special issue of *Romantic Pedagogies Commons* (July 2008) <https://romantic-circles.org/praxis/utopia/index.html>

John Larpent Plays. <https://oac.cdlib.org/findaid/ark:/13030/tf1h4n985c/> OAC. Online Archive of California. Fully searchable database of the official manuscript copies of plays submitted for licensing in Great Britain between 1737 and 1824. From the collection of John Larpent, the Examiner of Plays.

McEvoy, Benjamin. *Romantic Closet-Dramas: How to Revolutionise the Theatre* (19 May 2020) <https://benjaminmcevoy.com/romantic-closet-dramas-revolutionise-theatre/> Includes multimedia resources and videos

Miranda, Omar F. (ed.) *On the 200th Anniversary of Byron's Manfred* . *Commemorative Essays*. <https://romantic-circles.org/praxis/manfred> With Supplemental Video Material.

Mulhallen , Jacqueline. *The Theatre of Shelley*. New edition [online]. Cambridge: Open Book Publishers, 2010. Available on the Internet: <http://books.openedition.org/obp/744> . ISBN: 9781906924324.

Murray, Julie. "At the Surface of Romantic Interiority: Joanna Baillie's *Orra*." *Romanticism and Victorianism on the Net* 56 (november 2009), <https://doi.org/10.7202/1001091ar> <https://www.erudit.org/fr/revues/ravon/2009-n56-ravon1503285/1001091ar/>

Nielsen, Wendy, "'A Tragic Farce: Revolutionary Women in Elizabeth Inchbald's *The Massacre* and European Drama.'" *European Romantic Review* 17.3 (Summer 2006): 275-88." (2006). Department of English Faculty Scholarship and Creative Works. 16. <https://digitalcommons.montclair.edu/english-facpubs/16>

O'Shaughnessy, David. *THEATRONOMICS: The Business of Theatres, 1732-1809* ERC Grant ID: 101001052 <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101001052> . The EU-financed project will analyse

manuscript data from the two major London theatres, Covent Garden and Drury Lane. Among the items object of analysis: account books and ledgers, ticket sales, actor salaries etc.

O'Shaughnessy, David. *The Censorship of British Theatre, 1737-1843*.

<https://tobeomitted.tcd.ie/index.html> MSCA Project Grant ID: 333592 . Award-winning website which explores the topic of theatre censorship in Britain in the period 1737-1843.

Online Syllabi. <https://romantic-circles.org/pedagogies/syllabi/index.html> . Section: DRAMA. Award-winning syllabi in the area of Drama.

Portraits of Actors 1720-1920, Illinois Library Digital Collections.

<https://digital.library.illinois.edu/collections/81196b40-e3fb-012f-c5b6-0019b9e633c5-c> It includes studio portraits and actors posing in character or performing a scene from a play.

Reconstructing Early Circus. Entertainments at Asley's Amphitheatre, 1768-1833.

<https://dhil.lib.sfu.ca/circus/> A fully searchable, multimedia database of newspaper advertisements listing the featured acts at Astley's from 1768-1833.

Romantic Era Songs <https://www.sjsu.edu/faculty/douglass/music/index.html> Site maintained by Paul Douglass in collaboration with Frederick Burwick . The project is intended to make vocal music and lyrics of the of the Romantic period more accessible. I

Romantic Theatre Studies – State-of-the-Field and New Ways Forward. BARS DIGITAL EVENTS Series. Speakers included Sarah Burdett (The University of Warwick), Helen Dallas (University of Oxford), Essaka Joshua (The University of Notre Dame), David O'Shaughnessy (NUI Galway), Francesca Saggini (University of Edinburgh). Convened by Francesca Saggini.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FpMQkZp-NP8>

Rzepka, Charles, ed. *Obi: A Romantic Circles Praxis Volume*. (August 2002). <https://romantic-circles.org/praxis/obi/index.html>

Saggini, Francesca. *The Lady with the Balloon Hat*. <https://blogs.ed.ac.uk/fsaggini/> Blog for the MSCA Project *OpeRaNew – Opening Romanticism: Reimagining Romantic Drama for New Audiences* Grant agreement ID: 892230 (PI Francesca Saggini). The publicly financed project uses digital methods and literary analysis to establish an expanding multimedia framework to analyse and disseminate Frances Burney's plays <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/892230>

Saggini, Francesca. *The transforming muses: stage appropriations of the gothic novel in the 1790s*. PhD thesis, University of Glasgow (2009). <https://theses.gla.ac.uk/1473/>

Shannon, Mary L. and Dustin Frazier Wood (eds) *The Romantic Illustration Network Shakespeare Gallery* <https://romanticillustrationnetwork.com/shakespeare-gallery/> Images are arranged alphabetically by play. Site maintained by the University of Roehampton.

The R18 Collective. Re-Activating Restoration & 18th-Century Theatre for the 21st-Century.

<https://www.r18collective.org/> A multimedia website with research and teaching resources looking at the theatrical repertoire from the 1660s to the 1830s.

Urban, Eliza Dickinson. "Spectral Spectacle: Traps, Disappearances, and Disembodiment in Nineteenth-Century British Melodrama." *Nineteenth Century Theatre and Film* 46, 1 (May 2019): 18–37. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1748372718799081>.

<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/1748372718799081> (Open Epub)

Wood, Gillen D'Arcy (ed.). *Romanticism and Opera: A Romantic Circles Praxis Volume* (May 2005). <https://romantic-circles.org/praxis/opera/index.html> . A special issue considering the centrality of opera to Georgian culture.